

Study of Association of Pre-Eclampsia in Patients with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM)Rituparna Pattnaik¹, Sanghamitra Mohapatra², Bontha Krishnaveni³, Nina Mishra⁴¹PG Resident 3rd Year, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MKCG MCH, Berhampur²Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, MKCG MCH, Berhampur³MS, 3rd Year PG Resident, Department of obstetrics and gynaecology, Maharaja Krushna Chandra Gajapati Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur⁴M.D O&G, FIAOG, FICOG, Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, SRM MCH, Kalahandi

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Abstract:**Background:** Among the two most common complications of pregnancy, GDM and PE complicate pregnancies in a fashion that highly influences the health of mothers and fetuses. The principal objective of this study is thus to explore the relationship between GDM and PE based on maternal and fetal outcomes.**Methods:** This is a prospective observational study conducted at M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital from August 2022 to June 2024. We enrolled pregnant women diagnosed with GDM and followed them for the development of PE. Maternal outcome markers included change in blood pressure, adverse events, and mode of delivery. Fetal outcomes included birth weight, Apgar score, and neonatal complications.**Results:** Early data analysis indicates that GDM is strongly associated with the incidence of PE. The incidence of hypertension was also higher among women with GDM compared to those without GDM, reflecting a poor maternal outcome. Fetal outcome was varied regarding birth weight and Apgar scores, hence the maternal glucose influence on neonatal health.**Conclusion:** This study confirms that close follow-up of women with GDM prevents the onset of PE for the optimization of maternal and fetal outcomes. The underlying mechanism linking both conditions and strategies of intervention need further evaluation.**Keywords:** Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM), Preeclampsia (PE), Maternal Outcomes, Fetal Outcomes, Hypertension, Pregnancy Complications, Neonatal Health.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

GDM and PE are two of the most common and major complications of pregnancy, with both conditions frequently occurring together in women with predisposing factors like obesity, advanced maternal age, and multiple gestation. Both conditions have been extensively studied to share underlying pathophysiological mechanisms including increased oxidative stress, inflammation, and vascular endothelial dysfunction, all contributing to adverse fetomaternal outcomes [1]. Similarities like these raise doubt over both the possible etymological relation of GDM with the development of PE, and the increment in risk caused by them when found exclusively.

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus is a type of glucose intolerance that is diagnosed for the first time during pregnancy, usually between 24 and 28 weeks of gestation. IADPSG has proposed the criteria in the light of the HAPO study, which includes a 75-gram

OGTT for diagnosing GDM [2]. WHO further refined the criteria by proposing specific cut-offs for both fasting and postprandial glucose levels. In recent decades, GDM has emerged worldwide due to rising levels of obesity or changes in lifestyle factors. Today, the overall prevalence of GDM is reported to be in the range of 8.7 to 14% in various populations; rates as high as 15.2% are found in many parts of the world, including the Middle East and North Africa [3].

The predominant components of GDM pathogenesis are insulin resistance and β -cell dysfunction. In a normal pregnancy, women compensate for increased insulin resistance through enhanced insulin secretion. It is when pancreatic β -cells cannot respond adequately that GDM develops, especially in populations with pre-existing metabolic risks such as obesity [4]. GDM is not only a transient condition but is also associated with long-term metabolic

sequelae, including an increased risk of type 2 diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disease, and hypertension later in life. Besides this, GDM is also linked with perinatal complications, including macrosomia, neonatal hypoglycemia, and shoulder dystocia [5].

On the contrary, preeclampsia is described as de novo hypertension-vascularized systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg-after 20 weeks of gestation accompanied by proteinuria or features of multi-organ dysfunction such as renal or hepatic involvement. PE remains a leading cause of maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality, complicating approximately 3-8% of pregnancies [6]. The pathogenesis involves abnormal placentation, with inadequate trophoblastic invasion leading to insufficient remodeling of maternal spiral arteries. This results in placental ischemia and subsequent systemic endothelial dysfunction, which is characterized by an imbalance between angiogenic (eg, vascular endothelial growth factor [VEGF] and placental growth factor [PlGF]) and antiangiogenic (eg, soluble fms-like tyrosine kinase 1 [sFlt-1] and soluble endoglin [sEng]) factors [7].

Emerging evidence has documented a significant relationship between GDM and PE, with GDM increasing the risk for developing PE two to four times. Although the two conditions share common risk factors like obesity, nulliparity, advanced maternal age, and chronic hypertension, recent studies suggest that GDM itself may be an independent contributor to the development of PE. This may be a reflection of chronic insulin resistance, inflammation, and vascular endothelial dysfunction seen in GDM, which predispose patients to the hypertensive complications of pregnancy [8, 9].

The relationship between GDM and PE is complex and multifaceted. Whereas GDM induces a proangiogenic state, PE is characterized by antiangiogenic imbalance. This contrast may further worsen the clinical course of PE in women with GDM, leading to more serious maternal and neonatal complications. For both conditions, long-term health consequences have also been described with regard to cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and chronic hypertension for both mother and offspring. Children of mothers with GDM and/or PE are also at increased risk for obesity, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular disease later in life [10].

This study aims to explore the association between GDM and development of PE and further whether GDM acts as an independent risk factor for PE beyond their shared risk factors. It will also determine the maternal and fetal outcomes of pregnancy complications with both GDM and PE and those with GDM alone. Understanding their interaction is very much crucial for improvement in managing high-

risk pregnancies and also contributes to a reduction in adverse perinatal outcomes.

Methods

Study Design: The present prospective observational study was undertaken at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital. This study was undertaken with an aim to assess the association between preeclampsia (PE) and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) and its impact on maternal and fetal outcomes. Pregnant women diagnosed with GDM were followed for the development of preeclampsia and their outcomes were compared with a control group comprising women with GDM who did not develop PE.

Study Population: The study population included pregnant women presenting to the antenatal OPD of the hospital. The subjects were screened for GDM and later followed up for developing PE. A control group comprising women with GDM but no preeclampsia was selected to provide a comparison in maternal and fetal outcomes. The present study was undertaken with the aim of estimating the risk and impact of PE in the context of GDM.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Pregnant women with hyperglycemia first detected at or after 20 weeks of pregnancy and with no risk factors for diabetes in the past were included. Women with known GDM attending the antenatal OPD for the first time during the current pregnancy were also included.

The exclusion criteria included pregnant women on diabetogenic drugs, for example, corticosteroids, antiretroviral therapy; pre-existing type 1 or type 2 diabetes; pre-existing hypertension or cardiovascular diseases; and women with serious systemic illnesses such as cirrhosis, chronic renal failure, or untreated endocrine disorders like hyper- or hypothyroidism.

Screening and Diagnosis: We screened all eligible participants for GDM between 24 and 28 weeks using the DIPSI protocol. A 75-gram oral glucose load irrespective of the previous meal intake was administered, and plasma glucose levels were measured after 2 hours. Plasma glucose ≥ 140 mg/dL was considered as the diagnostic threshold for GDM. Participants diagnosed with GDM were followed up for the development of preeclampsia throughout their pregnancy.

Diagnosis of Preeclampsia: Preeclampsia was diagnosed in the case of new-onset hypertension (systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg) at or after 20 weeks of gestation, presented together with either proteinuria (urine dipstick test $\geq 1+$ albumin) or dysfunction in at least one organ including kidney, liver, blood system, or uteroplacental unit. Women who devel-

oped preeclampsia were encouraged to attend routine antenatal care visits and were advised to give birth in the hospital for close monitoring of maternal and fetal outcomes.

Data Collection: A structured checklist was used to record the sociodemographic profile, past obstetric history, and outcome of the pregnancy. Maternal outcome about hypertensive complications, cesarean delivery, and postpartum hemorrhage was noted. Fetal outcomes included preterm birth, low birth weight, IUGR, Apgar scores, and admissions to NICU were also noted. Patients with GDM and PE were compared to the patients with GDM without PE.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed thereafter with the use of SPSS software (version 17.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The results are presented as continuous variables for means and standard deviation. In addition, categorical variables are presented as counts and percentages. Comparisons of means

between groups were made by independent sample t-tests, while within groups they were made by paired t-tests. The Z-test was used to test the difference in proportions. All the tests were performed at a p-value ≤ 0.05 .

Ethical Considerations: The study is done strictly in accordance with ethical principles. The Institutional Ethics Committee, M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital had granted due approval. Written informed consent was taken from all participants in the local dialect after explaining the purpose and the methodology of the study. It was also made clear that they can withdraw at any stage without consequences, and confidentiality throughout the process would be maintained.

Results

In our study, 13 (13.0%) patients with GDM developed Pre-eclampsia i.e. association of pre-eclampsia in GDM patients was found to be 13% [Table 1].

Table 1: Development of Pre-eclampsia

Development of Pre-eclampsia	Number	GDM (Yes/No)	Percentage
No	87	No	87%
Yes	13	Yes	13%

In our study, 3 (3.0%) patients were <20 years of age, 80 (80.0%) patients were 21-30 years of age and 17 (17.0%) patients were 31-40 years of age [Table 2].

Table 2: Distribution of Age in Year

Age (Years)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Less than 20	3	3.0%
21 - 30	80	80.0%
31 - 40	17	17.0%
Total	100	100.0%

The table 3 shows that GDM is more common in primigravida (93.2%) whereas GDM associated with pre-eclampsia is more prevalent in multigravida (22%). The statistical test supports that these differences are significant. This p-value suggests a statistically significant association between gravidity and the condition ($p < 0.05$), indicating that the distribution of conditions differs between multigravida and primigravida patients.

Table 3: Distribution of Gravidity

Gravidity	Primi Frequency (%)	Multi Frequency (%)	Total Frequency (%)
GDM	32 (78.0%)	55 (93.2%)	87 (87.0%)
GDM + PE	9 (22.0%)	4 (6.8%)	13 (13.0%)
Total	41 (100.0%)	59 (100.0%)	100 (100.0%)

Chi-Square = 4.923, df = 1, p = 0.027

The GDM+PE group tends to have shorter gestational periods on average compared to the GDM group alone, with more variability in the timing of delivery. This could be due to the additional complications associated with preeclampsia [Table 4].

Table 4: Distribution of Mean Gestational Age

Group	Number	Mean Gestational Age (weeks)	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	38.6	1.25	34	41.3	38.6
GDM+PE	13	37.4	2.15	34	40.4	37.4

In our study, 5 (5.0%) patients had Decreased fetal movement, 10 (10.0%) patients had Leaking PV, 77 (77.0%) patients had Pain abdomen, and 2 (2.0%) patients had Past EDD as chief complaints.

Table 5: Distribution of Chief Complaint

Chief Complaint (C/C)	Frequency	Percent
BPV	1	1.0%
Decreased fetal movement	5	5.0%
Leaking PV	5	5.0%
No Complaint	10	10.0%
Pain abdomen	5	5.0%
Past EDD	77	77.0%
Total	100	100.0%

As shown in Table 6, the mean value of BMI is higher among the GDM+PE subjects with 29.8 compared to 26.7 for the subjects with GDM only. This suggests that GDM patients who are associated with preeclampsia tend to have a higher body mass index.

Table 6: Distribution of Mean BMI

Group	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	26.7	2.22	23.2	32.2	26.6
GDM + PE	13	29.8	4.28	21	34.5	31.3

From Table 7 and Table 8, the values of systolic and diastolic blood pressures from GDM+PE are significantly higher compared to patients with only GDM, 152 mmHg versus 122 mmHg and 94 mmHg versus 76.4 mmHg, respectively. These elevated blood pressures are the hallmark of pre-eclampsia.

Table 7: Distribution of Mean SBP (mmHg)

Condition	Number	Mean SBP	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	122	8.28	100	134	124
GDM + PE	13	152	7.85	140	160	154

Table 8: Distribution of Mean DBP (mmHg)

Condition	Number of Subjects	Mean DBP (mmHg)	SD	Minimum DBP (mmHg)	Maximum DBP (mmHg)	Median DBP (mmHg)
GDM	87	76.4	5.50	68	88	78
GDM+PE	13	94	6.22	82	100	92

Table 9 shows that all GDM+PE patients tested positive for urine albumin, indicating renal involvement in pre-eclampsia. Only 10.3% of GDM-only patients had positive results.

Table 9: Urine Albumin +ve

	GA 28WK	GA 32 WK	GA 36WK	Percentage
GDM (87)	NIL	NIL	9	10.3%
GDM+PE (13)	NIL	8	13	13%

The data [Table 10] indicates that women with both GDM and preeclampsia have significantly higher and more variable Sr AST levels compared to those with only GDM. Elevated AST levels are often associated with liver dysfunction or damage, which

can be indicative of the more severe pathophysiological conditions present in preeclampsia.

This suggests that preeclampsia may contribute to liver stress or damage in addition to gestational diabetes.

Table 10: Distribution of Mean Sr AST (IU/L)

Group	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	26.6	6.11	14	41	27
GDM + PE	13	59.8	34.6	18	118	56

The data [Table 11] indicates that women with both GDM and preeclampsia have significantly higher and more variable Sr ALT levels compared to those with only GDM. Elevated ALT levels are often associated with liver dysfunction or damage, which can occur in preeclampsia. This suggests that

preeclampsia may contribute to liver stress or damage beyond what is seen with gestational diabetes alone.

The high variability in the GDM+PE group suggests that the severity of liver involvement can vary widely among affected individuals.

Table 11: Distribution of Mean Sr ALT (IU/L)

Condition	Number of Patients	Mean Sr ALT (IU/L)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	18.3	5.49	10	32	18
GDM + PE	32	50.4	38.5	10	147	40

The data [Table 12] indicates that women with both GDM and preeclampsia have significantly higher and more variable serum uric acid levels compared to those with only GDM. Elevated uric acid levels are often associated with preeclampsia and can be a marker of increased oxidative stress and metabolic disturbances.

Table 12: Distribution of Mean Sr UA (mg/Dl)

Group	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	4.5	1	3	7	4.2
GDM + PE	13	6.66	1.72	3.3	8.9	6.3

The data [Table 13] indicates that the GDM+PE group exhibits higher average values and greater variability for the serum creatinine values compared to the GDM group. This pattern may reflect a more pronounced effect or condition in the GDM+PE group.

Table 13: Distribution of Mean Sr CREAT (mg/Dl)

Group	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	0.556	0.178	0.1	0.9	0.5
GDM + PE	13	1.2	0.524	0.5	2	1.3

Overall, the data [Table 14] shows that women with both GDM and preeclampsia have significantly higher and more variable Sr LDH levels compared to those with only GDM. Elevated LDH lev-

els are often associated with cell damage and increased metabolic activity, which can be indicative of the more severe pathophysiological conditions present in preeclampsia.

Table 14: Distribution of Mean Sr LDH (U/L)

Group	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	411	120	210	867	440
GDM + PE	13	972	548	542	2343	790

The data [Table 15] indicates that women with GDM have a higher average platelet count and greater variability in platelet counts compared to women with both GDM and preeclampsia. The GDM+PE group, while having a lower mean plate-

let count, shows similar median values to the GDM group, with less variability. This may reflect the effects of preeclampsia on platelet levels, which can vary widely due to the condition's impact on the cardiovascular and hemostatic systems.

Table 15: Distribution of Mean Total Platelet Count

Group	Number	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum	Median
GDM	87	231828	79658	101000		
GDM + PE	13	431000	132000	101000	211000	146154

Discussion

The present study was undertaken to find the association between PE and GDM within the cohort of pregnant women attending the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology at M.K.C.G. Medical College & Hospital from August 2022 to June 2024. The findings will bring out the significant prevalence of PE in the patients diagnosed with GDM, which is important in the light of maternal and fetal outcomes [11].

Our findings indicated that 13% of women with GDM developed preeclampsia, which is comparable to the 12.4% incidence reported in a related study by Joffe et al. (1998). This prevalence acts as an indicator of the utmost importance of cautious

monitoring of hypertensive disorders in GDM-complicated pregnancies. Akinyemi et al. (2023) highlighted that GDM is one of the major causes of poor pregnancy outcomes worldwide, which was also evident from our research findings [12]. The demographic medians for the age of presentation of GDM among women in our cohort were considerably younger; the majority (67%) were between 21 and 30 years of age. This is in comparison to the findings by Akinyemi et al., who reported that the median age was 31 years among women presenting with GDM. These observations, thus, support partly the view that the variability in the age distribution can be related to the regional and contextual factors in the GDM epidemiology and, therefore, need specific approaches in health care [13].

For obstetric history, our study revealed that GDM was preponderantly encountered in primigravida patients, even though a higher proportion of GDM associated with PE was found in multigravida patients (22%). The statistical significance of the latter finding ($p < 0.05$) points out that gravidity should be taken into consideration in analyzing the risk factors for PE among women with GDM. The potential relationship between gravidity and PE may be due to the fact that the risk factors involved are acquired during successive pregnancies [14]. The clinical manifestations in our cohort included abdominal pain, which was the chief complaint of 76% of the patients. Though most women with isolated GDM did not present with pedal edema, PE with GDM did present quite often with the symptom, making it a very important symptom in the clinical evaluation of hypertensive disorders. The statistical significance of this symptom is $p < 0.00001$, which corresponds to literature where pedal edema is documented as a classic symptom of PE [15].

Laboratory findings also indicated that a significant percentage of the women who had both GDM and PE tested positive for urinary albumin, 22%, which is indicative of renal involvement characteristic of PE. This is statistically significant at $p < 0.00001$ and further supports recommendations for renal function monitoring in this population. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that during PE, the kidneys could be affected as a result of increased blood pressure and subsequent vascular changes [16]. Of note, our analysis identified the significant association of GDM with preterm delivery; this complication accounted for 9% of patients with preeclampsia. Supportingly, there is literature evidence linking PE with adverse perinatal outcomes including preterm birth and FGR (Zhang et al., 2019). Moreover, in GDM patients with PE, we encountered only one case of intrauterine growth restriction, reflecting very high risk of fetal complications in such cases [17]. In addition, APH was present only in patients with GDM combined with PE, and this association is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This means that coexistence significantly enhances the risk for APH and perhaps justifies more active surveillance and management strategies for these women. The absence of APH in GDM-alone patients also justifies the need for closer follow-up of this high-risk group [18]. Fetal outcomes also showed disturbing trends, and our study established that 13% of newborns with birth asphyxia leading to NICU admissions were born to mothers with co-existent GDM and PE. This correlation was statistically significant, with a p-value of less than 0.00001, and supports the findings of Pankiewicz et al. (2022), who reported a strong association between GDM, PE, and adverse neonatal outcomes [19].

Biochemical maternal parameters significantly differed in women with GDM and PE. The mean serum LDH level was profoundly elevated, as observed: 483.98 ± 291.57 U/L, representing cellular injury that can eventually result in organs malfunctioning. The findings agree with a recent investigation by Lara-Barea et al., 2022, which demonstrated changes in blood pressure and other biochemical markers associated with perinatal complications [20].

In sum, this review highlights the critical intersection between GDM and preeclampsia, thus signifying their active monitoring and management. The association of PE with GDM is a concern for maternal health and requires healthcare providers to assume proactive measures to detect it early for early intervention. Future studies are thus needed to investigate the underlying mechanisms of the link between GDM and PE, including the development of targeted strategies in mitigating the risks in this vulnerable population. Increased awareness and individualized care approaches will therefore play a vital role in improving outcomes for mothers and infants.

Conclusion

This study has shown a significant association with preeclampsia and gestational diabetes mellitus at a prevalence of 13% among gestational diabetes mellitus patients, hence, gestational diabetes mellitus being a significant risk factor toward the development of preeclampsia. Advanced maternal age, multiparity, and higher baseline body mass index appeared to be the major contributing factors to this risk. More than that, in the patients with GDM who developed PE, there were higher rates of maternal and neonatal complications in the form of premature deliveries with notably higher rates of cesarean sections, together with an elevation in a number of their biochemical markers such as serum creatinine, uric acid, and liver enzymes. The findings bring out the imperative need for vigilant monitoring and management of GDM to reduce the incidence of PE and improve pregnancy outcomes. Besides, this study adds to the very few that have explored this relationship; limitations such as small sample size and single-center design make it mandatory to undertake further multicentric studies for a full understanding of this intricate relationship and developing the best strategies for optimizing health in both mothers and neonates.

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